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Research Paper

Evaluation of the Antibacterial Potential of *Rhododendron arboretum* Flower Extract against Pathogenic Bacteria

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ABSTRACT

Rhododendron arboreum is an evergreen plant and widely distributed in Himalayas from Kashmir to Nagaland at an altitude ranging from 1500-5500 meter and this is one of the plant that have great economical and medicinal importance. Rhododendron arboreum is also called burans or gurans. There are more than one thousand species of Rhododendron in worldwide. R. arboreum plant used for the treatment of various human diseases which include the infectious diseases caused by microorganisms. R. arboreum was analysed for the antibacterial activity. Antibacterial activity of the methanol, acetone, chloroform, petroleum ether and aqueous extract of R. arboreum used against the microorganism gram+ve and gram-ve strains. The antibacterial activity was evaluated by measuring the zone of inhibition using disc diffusion method. The chemical constituents of R. arboreum are hollocellulose, hemicelluloses, alpha-cellulose, pentosans, lignins and fatty acids are butonic acid, pentonic acid, 4-heptanoic acid. The inhibition activity of flower extract of R. arboreum was absorbed on gram+ve bacteria i.e. Mycobacterium bacillus (8.90 ± 0.00mm zone) at 30ml methanolic extract and gram -ve bacteria i.e. Pseudomonas salmonella (9.20 ± 2.00 mm zone) at 30ml chloroform extract. Using various solvents, petroleum ether showed no inhibitory effect while methanol, acetone and chloroform extracts was quite effective against all pathogens even in low concentration. The present review is an effort to give the detailed survey of literature on its pharmacognosy, phytochemistry and pharmacological uses of plant under study.

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INTRODUCTION

Rhododendron was derived from the Greek word 'rhodo' means 'rose' and 'dendron' means 'tree' which belong to family *Ericaceae* [1] and was first described by Carl Linnaeus in 1837[19]. It is the National flower of Nepal (Laligurans), state flower of Sikkim and Himachal Pradesh (Burans), and also the state tree of Uttarakhand[2]. First Rhododendron was coming from Southeastern Asia. The tree species of *R.arboreum* was discovered by Captin Hardwicke in 1799. It was arrived in India 1811. In 1821 Don was introduced two species i.e. *R.anthropogen* and *R.setosum* from Asia. The first hybrid species of Rhododendron was introduced from China. Worldwide, around 1200 species of Rhododendron have been estimated among which China has the highest number of species that is 571 species of total species in the world, of which 404 endemics [17]. In India, there are about 80 species, 10 subspecies and 14 varieties. The existing record indicate that 98% of the Indian species are found in the Himalayan region [18]. The native places are Bhutan, China, India, Nepal and Pakistan [3]. In India, it is mainly found in J&K, H.P. and Uttarakhand. In Himachal Pradesh, it is found in Chamba, Kangra, Kullu, Shimla, Mandi, Kinnaur and Sirmour districts. India is the major center for research of natural products and safer alternatives of medicine. Indian Himalayan Region (IHR) is one of the major hot-spots for medicinal plant species and Himachal is one of the bioresource rich and full of potential opportunities [4]. According to WHO (2000), 65% of the world's population integrate the medicinal plant for treatment and 80% of the Indian population used plant product for treating many diseases [20]. Infectious diseases are the number one among all causes of death. About 50-75% of the hospital deaths are reported due to infectious diseases caused by microorganism [21]. In developing

countries, traditional medicine is one of the primary healthcare systems [22]. Many herbs are used in the traditional medicine and their curvatures potentials are well documented [23]. Rhododendron arboreum is an evergreen plant and widely distributed in Himalayas from Kashmir to Nagaland at an altitude ranging from 1500-5500 meter [5]. About 65% of newly drugs developed between 1981 to 2005 which were depends upon natural herbs and specially play a important role area of life threatening disease [24]. The natural products provide various elements which are useful for molecular diversity and some biological functionality, which leads to novel drug delivery. In ancient days, bacterial resistance to antibiotics has become a serious therapeutic problem. The rare of new antibiotics are produced slowly. In the present time aqueous and alcoholic extracts methods were subjected for antibacterial activity against gram+ve bacteria (*Mycobacterium bacillus*) and gram -ve bacteria (*Pseudomonas salmonella*) [6]. Flower of *R.arboreum* contain phenols, saponins, xanthoprotein, steroids, tannins and coumarin. More plant rich in secondary metabolites which have been found in vitro to have antibacterial properties [25]. It also contains minerals such as manganese, iron, zinc, copper, sodium, chromium, nickel, lead and arsenic. Minerals play a vital role in maintaining certain physicochemical processes which are essential for life. Manganese, copper, selenium, zinc, iron are important cofactor found in the structure of certain enzymes and are indispensable in numerous biochemical pathway. Sodium is important in maintain the osmotic balance between cells and interstitial fluid [16]. Traditionally the *R.arboreum* is used for the treatment of various diseases like diarrhea, headache [7]. Some experiments shows that *R.arboreum* has phytochemical activity which is used to cure human diseases like diabetes [8], inflammation, bacterial and fungal infection [9].

Figure No. 1: *Rhododendron arboretum*

Table 1: Scientific Classification *Rhododendron arboretum*

Kingdom	Plantae
Clade	Tracheophytes
Clade	Angiosperms
Clade	Eudicots
Clade	Asterids
Order	Ericales
Family	Ericaceae
Subfamily	Ericoideae
Tribe	Rhodoreae
Genus	Rhododendron

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

- **Collection:** The *Rhododendron arboretum* flowers were collected from area of distt. Mandi, Himachal Pradesh, India and used for the treatment of antibacterial diseases.
- **Processing of Flower Material:** Flower of *R. arboretum* were collected from respective plant, washed thoroughly under distilled water. After that the flower were cut into smaller pieces for quick drying. Cleaned flowers were shade dried for 15-20 days. The dried plant material were crushed into fine powder with the help of pestle mortar. Finally the fine powder was stored in air tight container at room temperature [10].
- **Extraction Methods:**
The extraction of *Rhododendron arboretum* flower was done with solvent-solvent extraction method. It is divided into two types:
 - 1. Aqueous extraction method:** Take 5g powdered form of flower extract in a beaker and add sufficient amount of water in which flower

powder immersed completely. After that chloroform was added as a preservative and placed aside for 72 hours with alternate stirring. Filter the material and get brown colour extract and this extract dried in desiccator.

- 2. Alcoholic extraction method:** Take 5g powdered form of flower extract and packed into the Soxhlet apparatus. The material was subjected to continuous hot percolation for 8-9 hours with 175ml methanol. The obtained extract was semi-solid and dried in desiccator [13].

Determination of Antibacterial Activity:

- 1. Test organism:** The pure cultures of bacteria maintained in the microbiology laboratory were used for the microbiological work. The test organisms were maintained on agar medium [6]. The antibacterial activity of *R. arboretum* flower extract was assessed against to bacterial species gram+ve and gram-ve bacteria. The gram+ve

bacteria were *Mycobacterium bacillus* and *Lactobacillus*. The gram-ve bacteria were *Pseudomonas salmonella*.

2. Antibacterial screening: It can be done by various methods. The methods are:

- Agar disc diffusion method
- Broth or agar dilution method
- Broth microdilution method
- Broth macrodilution method

Agar disc diffusion method: This method developed in 1940 and in present days this method is used in many clinical microbiology laboratories for antibacterial testing. *Mycobacterium bacillus*, *Lactobacillus* and *Pseudomonas salmonella* using specific culture media, various incubation condition for inhibition zone [11].

PROCEDURE:

- The nutrient agar media was prepared in the conical flask and sterilized into the autoclave.
- Add the culture media into two different petri plates in the aseptic condition or in laminar hood and left for solidify.

- In first petri plate, add the gram+ve bacteria (*Mycobacterium bacillus*, *Lactobacillus*) and solidify for 5 minutes.
- In the second petri plate, add the gram-ve bacteria (*Pseudomonas salmonella*) and also solidify for 5 minutes.
- In both petri plates, pore with the help of borer.
- After that add alcoholic or aqueous extract of *R.arboreum* flower in pores of the petri plates and keep the plates into the incubator at 30°C to 35°C.
- After 24 to 48 hours of incubation, if the microorganism is susceptible for plant extract, zone of inhibition was visible.
- Measure the diameter of the clear zone [12].

Agar disc diffusion method is not appropriate to determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC). It is impossible to determine quantitative amount of antimicrobial agent diffuse into the agar media [14]. The advantages of disc diffusion method are low cost, simplicity, ability to test various microorganisms and antimicrobial agents [15].

Preparation of extracts:

Solvent	P.S.	Parameters
Methanol	1:20	35°C, 120rpm for 24 hours.
Acetone		
Chloroform		
Petroleum ether		

RESULT AND DISCUSSION: In the present study, *Rhododendron arboreum* was tested for their antibacterial properties against selected human pathogens. Result obtained revealed that the tested plant extracts possess considerable potential antibacterial activity against

Mycobacterium bacillus, *Lactobacillus*, *Pseudomonas salmonella*.

% Inhibition of growth of pathogenic bacterial at different concentration of methanol, acetone, chloroform and petroleum ether extract of *R. arboretum*:

Extract	Concentration in %	Inhibition of diameter (in mm)		
		<i>Mycobacterium bacillus</i>	<i>Lactobacillus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas salmonella</i>
Methanol extract	Control	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
	10	6.65 ± 0.35	6.28 ± 0.10	3.25 ± 0.11
	20	7.88 ± 1.00	6.99 ± 0.15	5.45 ± 0.22

	30	8.90 ± 1.20	8.00 ± 0.10	6.58 ± 1.00
Acetone extract	Control	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
	10	4.55 ± 0.00	5.55 ± 0.01	2.65 ± 0.22
	20	5.05 ± 1.05	6.03 ± 1.02	3.45 ± 1.11
	30	5.99 ± 1.35	6.49 ± 1.11	4.45 ± 2.12
Chloroform extract	Control	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
	10	3.22 ± 1.05	3.44 ± 0.02	8.88 ± 0.11
	20	3.55 ± 1.10	3.78 ± 0.11	9.02 ± 1.01
	30	4.05 ± 2.00	4.02 ± 1.20	9.20 ± 2.02
Petroleum ether	Control	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
	10	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
	20	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
	30	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00

Each data represent mean of three replicates ± S.D

CONCLUSION:

Using different extracts petroleum ether did not show any inhibitory effect against Mycobacρείum bacillus, Lactobacillus, Pseudomonas salmonella. Extract were used in different-different concentration i.e.10,20,30ml of extract had been found maximum effective against all three pathogens. Chloroform extract of the leaves of the R.arboreum was more effective against gram+ve bacteria. In general using chloroform gram -ve bacteria was more resistant than gram +ve bacteria. Methanol extract was found to be more effective against selected pathogenic bacterial as compared to acetone, ethanol extract. Methanol extract of the leaves of R.arboreum was more effective against gram +ve bacteria. In general using mrthanol extract gram +ve bacteria was more resistant than gram –ve bacteria.

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